

RES4CITY CASE STUDY #2

Pre-feasibility study of
**Cold ironing for
cruise ships**

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Executive Summary

Figure 2. Pre-feasibility study of the cold ironing for cruise ship. A 3E Analysis - Graphical Abstract

This case study evaluates the application of cold ironing technology as an alternative to using auxiliary or main engines powered by marine fuel oil to supply cruise ships with energy during the hotelling phase. By calculating energy consumption, pollutant emissions and externality costs for both on-board production and cold ironing for a cruise ship in an Italian port

(Figure 2), the results show that cold ironing technology reduces fossil fuel consumption and greenhouse gas and air pollutant emissions, while ensuring economic viability. Assuming a connection fee of 46 €/MWh, the estimated savings per cruise ship are 9 M€ in fuel savings over 30 years and 31 M€ per year in externality costs.

Abstract

Freight and passenger transport is continuously growing, including the cruise sector which is an increasing business field for ports and cities that generates an additional income for the city and related economic sectors. On the other hand, anchoring ships have relevant energy consumption, noise generation, and pollutant emissions which have a substantial environmental impact. This issue is tighter when ports are closed or connected with urban areas, as often happens.

It is estimated that 10%-15% of harmful emissions occur in the port. Even though most of the emissions happens during the navigation, port emissions have a relevant impact on the urban areas of many EU cities, thus it is fundamental to highlight solutions for the reduction of the pollutant emissions.

An effective option to decrease energy consumption and the corresponding pollutant emissions of anchoring ships is to switch the energy supply modality, namely from ship-based to land-based modality.

The land-based modality consists in shifting energy generation from the ship to the land. Thus, the ship is supplied with energy generated somewhere else. In particular, the power load is covered with electricity generated in another location (ideally renewable based generation) while decreasing at minimum the load of ship engines. This approach, known as “cold ironing”, drastically reduces the emissions while the ship is anchoring.

The present case study will develop an energy, environmental, and economic (3E) analysis of the impact of “cold ironing” of a cruise ship anchoring in an Italian port.

The analysis demonstrated that the cold ironing is a viable option from energy, environmental, and economic point of view.

In particular, a connection fee of 46 €/MWh is estimated for the cold ironing system.

Furthermore, the cold ironing guarantees fuel savings of 9 M€ in a period of 30 years for a cruise ship anchoring. The impact of the reduction in the externality cost is much more substantial and estimated in 31 M€/year per cruise ship. The analysis is developed for one cruise ship and it can be easily extended to evaluate the impact on one port or on the Italian cruise ship sector.

Introduction

In port emissions are a relevant issue for vessels anchored in ports especially when the port is located close to the urban areas. The problem is not negligible since maritime traffic constantly increased during the years. In terms of pollutant emissions, NO_x, SO₂ and soot emissions are the typical ones in addition a substantial amount of carbon emissions is also released.

Among the different typologies of vessels, cruise ships can be considered one of the most pollutant one while hotelling in ports since they need to provide services for a large amount of people (i.e., 5k-10k passengers) thus provoking a substantial environmental impact.

The problem is highlighted in the scientific and technical literature and different authors analysed it in various countries. Maragkogianni & Papaefthimiou (2015) studied the level of emissions from cruise ships in the first 5 Greek ports. They found that emissions during the hotelling represent the 85% of the total and largely exceeded those related to manoeuvring which represented 12%. Furthermore, seasonality has a significant effect on the level of emissions which are concentrated in summer season due to the higher cruise traffic.

For reducing the emissions level most ship-owners prefer to pollutant emissions reducing systems such as Scrubbers and Selective Catalytic Reactor

Systems which can be connected with internal combustion engines (ICE) burning heavy fuel oil (Armellini et al., 2019). An alternative solution could be the utilization of a gas turbine fuelled with Marine Gas Oil combined with an ICE and tri-generation systems in order to exploit the positive features of all the systems as discussed by (Armellini et al., 2019).

Emissions from cruise ships in ports determine social cost for the neighbouring port areas and (Tichavska & Tovar, 2015) developed an analysis for the quantification of the externality costs from cruise ships in the port of Las Palmas in Tenerife.

Detailed bottom-up calculation of the emissions from cruise ships in Greek ports, i.e., 18 ports investigated, demonstrated that more than 89% of the emissions are due to the hotelling and the enlargement of the tourism season in October and

November has extended the period of exposure of the population in nearby areas to high emissions levels (Papaefthimiou et al., 2016). Other authors implemented machine learning tools to determine the emissions from cruise ships as is the case of Barcelona port (Fabregat et al., 2022).

The analysis of the environmental and social impact of cruise tourism is object of many studies since researchers attempt to understand if the environmental cost is offset by a social gain in terms of improvement of social conditions of people living in urban areas close to cruise ports.

MacNeill & Wozniak (2018) proposed a methodology to measure the economic, social, and environmental impact of cruise tourism on a local community. They tested their methodology in the Trujillo-area cruise ship project in Honduras. They detected an improvement of the safety of

the area, since crime decreased due to increase of spending in police services, but they also noted an increase of pollution and corruption. These results cannot be generalized overall but they can be an indication of possible effects especially in developing countries.

Carić & Mackelworth (2014) discussed the overall environmental impact from cruise tourism, including waste and sewage water, in the Mediterranean Sea with a specific focus on Croatia which is an emerging destination. They observe that the level of consumption of cruise passengers is often much higher than those of people in local communities hosting cruise ships thus the resource consumption and consequent emissions of cruise tourists overcome those of residents. Furthermore, they estimate that the environmental cost can be up to seven times higher with respect to the economic benefits to local Croatian communities.

Johnson (2002) proposed a categorization to highlight which are the action that cruise operators and cruise destinations can implement to reduce the environmental impact of cruise tourism. Similarly, Klein (2011) analysed possible pathlines for the sustainable development of cruise tourism by focusing on three dimensions, namely environmental impact on coastal and marine environment, local economies, and socio-cultural aspects of local ports communities.

An innovative approach to reduce the environmental impact of cruise ships while hotelling is the utilization of the so-called cold ironing, namely the onshore electricity supply to the vessel for ensuring all the necessary activities. This approach consents to switch off the engines or to reduce their power substantially and, consequently, a total or

relevant reduction of the pollutant emissions is achieved locally. On the other hand, if the power generation mix of the country is low carbon intensive, there is an overall positive environmental benefit since the global amount of pollutants and carbon emissions is reduced.

This approach attracted the interest of many scholars who investigated the issue and proposed different solutions and analyses. Ballini & Bozzo (2015) studied the socio-economic benefits of implementing cold ironing for cruise ships. They implemented the Economic Evaluation of Air Pollution model, EVA, and estimated that if 60% of the cruise ships in Copenhagen would use cold ironing, a saving in externality of 3 M€/year is achieved.

Innes & Monios (2018) developed the feasibility analysis of cold ironing in a medium size port, namely Aberdeen. They estimated

that the external cost benefits would be able to repay the investment in a period of 3.5-7 years.

Caprara et al. (2021) studied the possibility to implement cold ironing in cruise port of Civitavecchia, near Rome. They concluded that the current port facilities do not allow to sustain cold ironing since they are unable to supply the necessary power. On the other hand, they suggest developing an electrical storage system to support the current infrastructure and to exploit possible local for renewable energy sources.

Sciberras et al. (2016) analyse the different electrical configurations available for cold ironing. They modelled the different approaches by using real operational data from European ports. They conclude that carbon emissions can be reduced by up to 40%.

Zis et al. (2014) propose a methodology for the analysis of pollutant and carbon emissions

reduction in ports using cold ironing. Based on their methodology, they evaluated the impact of different emission reduction policies.

Finally, Zis (2019) developed a review to provide a picture on the state of art of the implementation of this technology and the barriers hampering its wide diffusion. Abu Bakar et al. (2023) also propose a complete review of studies related to cold ironing. In particular, they provide an overview of calculation methodologies for emissions and costs assessment.

Based on previous analyses, the present document proposes the development of a case study to estimate the energy, environmental, and economic impact of implementing cold ironing for cruise ships in Italian ports. The topic is of paramount importance since Italy is one of the world's leading touristic destinations and in 2023 about 5000 cruise ship dockings are foreseen.

Description of Case Study

The present case study focuses on the application of the cold ironing technology for supplying energy to cruise ships while hoteling (i.e. when they stop in ports). Cruise ships need relevant amount of energy while hoteling since all the services for the boarded tourists (i.e., air conditioning, warm water, electricity supply) are active. This energy is normally supplied by using auxiliary engines or main engines fuelled with marine fuel oil.

This determines a relevant environmental, but also noise impact, of cruise ships in ports, especially when port infrastructures are close to city centres. Based on this, the mitigation of the environmental impact is necessary.

An effective way to reduce both environmental and noise pollution could be the electrification of the consumption by providing

onshore electricity as is usually done with yachts. On the other hand, the power necessary to supply a cruise ship is much higher, i.e., in the range of 10-20 MW, thus a robust infrastructure in terms of power transmission and generation is needed.

Furthermore, it must be added that the environmental sustainability of the cold ironing approach depends on the power generation mix of the individual country where it is implemented. The higher is the share of renewables and the more sustainable is to implement the cold ironing.

The present case study will analyse the implementation of the cold ironing for cruise ship in the Italian context. The analysis will consider the electrification of one cruise dock to analyse its energy, environmental, and economic feasibility.

Case Study Solution

The proposed methodology consists in the calculation of on-board and onshore energy and pollutant emissions; thus, the savings can be estimated.

On-board total power supply is given by the sum of the operation of the main engine, the auxiliary engine and the boiler according to Equation 1.

$$P_{Tot} = P_{ME} \cdot LF + P_{Aux} + P_B \quad (1)$$

Where LF is the load factor of the main engine set at 20% as suggested in (Bacalja, et al., 2020). Table 2 reports the main features of the different engines.

Table 2. Power of the different engines during the hotelling phase (Smith, et al., 2015)

	Main Engine	Auxiliary	Boiler
Power [MW]	7.2	7.5	0.8
Specific Consumption [g/kWh]	208	225	300

By multiplying P_{Tot} for the hotelling time, H , the total energy consumption is obtained, as given in Equation 2:

$$EC = P_{Tot} \cdot H \quad (2)$$

The consumption of fuel oil is determined by multiplying the energy generated by each engine for its specific consumption, as given in Equation 3:

$$FOC_i = SC_i \cdot EC_i \quad (3)$$

Where i is referred to main engine, auxiliary engine, and boiler. Once estimated the fuel oil

consumption, it is possible to obtain the pollutant, i.e., NO_x , SO_x , and soot, and the carbon emissions by multiplying the oil consumption for the corresponding emission factors as highlighted by Equation 4:

$$EM_j = FOC \cdot EF_j \quad (4)$$

Where EM are the j -th emission typology (i.e., NO_x , SO_x , soot, and CO_2) and EF is the corresponding emission factor. EF values are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Emission factors for on-board and onshore generation (City & Port Development, 2015), (Becker, et al., 2008).

	CO ₂ [g/kWh]	NO _x [g/kWh]	SO _x [g/kWh]	PM [mg/kWh]
Marine Gasoil	645	13.2	0.2	207
Coal	925	2.5	2.5	80
Fuel Oil	872	2.6	1.2	130
Natural Gas	461	0.5	0.03	10

Energy consumption and emissions from on-board generation are compared to those from onshore generation.

Onshore emissions depend on the power supply mix of the considered country, namely by the share of coal, natural gas, and fuel oil power generation facilities in the power generation fleet. The higher is the share of renewables and the lower are emission levels.

By multiplying the emissions factor for the share of the different fossil power generation sources, the emissions are obtained with a relation similar to Eq. (4),

where FOC is substitute with the considered fuel (e.g., coal, fuel oil, natural gas, waste, etc.) available in the energy mix.

Eqs. (1)-(4) allow to determine the energy consumption of cruise ships during the hotelling phase and the corresponding emissions, thus they consent to estimate the energy and environmental performance of the two solutions on a daily basis. To estimate the yearly impact, it is necessary to multiply EC, FOC, and EM for the days of the year, i.e., 365, and for a load factor which considers the effective operational day of the cruise ship in one year. The basis assumption in this work is consider a yearly load factor of 50% for a cruise ship.

In addition to the energy and environmental performance, the economic viability should be assessed. Thus, the NPV, Eq. (5) is calculated by using a hurdle rate as discount factor. In such a way it is possible to determine the minimum sale price of the electricity to cruise ships in order to have a profitable investment.

$$NPV = -INV + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{CIS_i \cdot E_i - COS_i}{(1+HR)^i} \quad (5)$$

Where INV is the investment cost for developing the power connection to supply the dock, E is the electrical energy supplied to the ship, CIS is the selling price of the cold ironing service, COS groups all the possible costs (i.e., O&M), n is the operating life of the infrastructure, i is the year index, and HR is the hurdle rate (i.e., the wanted rate of return for the project). HR is set at 12% as base case. By setting NPV equal to zero, thus the wanted rate of return is guaranteed, it is possible to estimate the price of electricity, supposed constant in real terms, to apply.

CIS must be added to the electricity price and this total cost for cold ironing is to be compared with the cost of the traditional energy supply (e.g., fuel oil used onboard). If the total cost for cold ironing is lower than it can be said that it represents the most convenient solution.

To make a more in-depth study, externality costs of onboard and onshore energy generation are also considered. Since the hotelling is a relevant source of air pollutant and greenhouse gas emissions, externalities connected with SO_x, NO_x, PM, and CO₂ emissions are considered.

In consideration of the fact that most of the port infrastructures are located close to densely populated areas, the impact of externality costs is relevant and it could also represent the main decision driver.

Results and Discussion

By applying the methodology illustrated in the previous section, it is possible to determine the energy consumption of a cruise ship during the hotelling phase. According to Eq. (1), the average load during the hotelling phase is 15.5 MW and, since the duration of the hotelling is estimated in 10 hours, i.e., usually the central part of the

day, while the night is reserved to the navigation, the energy consumption is equal to 155 MWh.

This energy can be supplied in different ways, namely through on-board generation or through cold ironing facilities. If the supply is guaranteed through on-board generation, to estimate the average consumption of marine gasoil, the average fuel specific consumption is multiplied for the energy supply and a total of 34 t/day of fuel is obtained.

If a cold ironing facility is considered to supply the necessary energy, the primary energy consumption depends on the power generation mix of the correspondent power system (e.g., in case the port object of the study is in Italy, primary energy consumption for power generation will depend on the Italian mix). The present study considers the Italian energy mix and it takes into account the average pre-covid generation

mix where RES generation has the 32% of the share versus the 68% of fossil fuels as shown by IEA data for Italy. In terms of fossil fuel consumption for power generation, the following share estimated: 32% coal, 12% fuel oil, 53% natural gas, and 3% waste.

Pre-covid values are considered in order to be conservative with respect to peculiar effect

connected with the specific period rather than with the evolution of the power system. In such a way possible distortions are avoided.

Once known the fossil fuel energy consumption in both cases, it is possible to determine the pollutant emissions by considering appropriate emission factors as shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Emission factors and externality costs of air pollutants and greenhouse gas emissions

Emission Factor	SOx	NOx	PM	CO2
Emission Factor on-board Generation [g/kWh]	0.2	13.2	0.207	645
Emission Factor onshore Generation [g/kWh]	1.0	1.4	0.049	672
Externality Cost [€/kg]	12.3	27.4	109	0.1

Figure 3. Air pollutant emissions and carbon emissions in case of on-board and onshore energy supply during the hotelling phase for a cruise ship.

Figure 3 highlights that the pollutant emissions are generally lower when onshore generation, i.e., cold ironing, is considered. In particular, NOx, PM, and CO2 emissions are noticeably lower. On the contrary SO2 emissions are lower in case of on-board generation. SO2 emissions are higher in power generation mainly due to the presence of

coal in the power mix, furthermore marine fuel oil has a low sulphur content, thus its emission coefficient is very low. Pollutant emission coefficients for the onshore generation vary according to the power generation mix. For example, in the extreme case of a 100% RES system, the average pollutant emission coefficients will be equal to

zero and no pollutant emissions (or very limited amounts if overall life cycle is considered) are emitted.

The overall impact due to the reduction of pollutant and greenhouse gas emissions can be estimated by considering the reduction of the externalities. It is calculated that the total externality cost in case of on-board generation is equal to 33 M€/year, whereas in case of onshore generation it is equal to 2.4 M€/year. Thus, if cold ironing is implemented in Italy a saving of 31 M€/year/cruise ship is achieved. This is a substantial saving also in consideration that a lot of people is involved since cruise port terminals are usually located close to city centres.

Externality saving has a crucial role in the decision process if the cold ironing infrastructure is financed by public institutions with public money.

The CAPEX for developing a cold ironing infrastructure to connect a cruise ship with an average load of maximum 20

MW is about 10 M€ (City & Port Development, 2015). If an operating life of 30 years, a hurdle rate of 12%, O&M cost of 0.1 M€2021/year, and a yearly load factor of 50% are considered, a connection fee of 46 €/MWh is necessary to have NPV=0 according to Eq. (5). This connection fee will make the investment profitable (i.e., the hurdle rate includes both the WACC and the target profitability). On top of the connection fee, the electricity cost must be added.

The cost of power supply is estimated by hypothesizing that the combined cycle gas turbine (CCGT) will be the marginal technology, i.e., the one setting the price on the power market, during the whole operating life of the cold ironing system. This is in line with the current and next future structure of the Italian power system (Bianco & Scarpa, 2018).

Thus, natural gas and CO₂ cost evolutions are

considered according to the World Energy Outlook “Stated Policy Scenario” (IEA, 2022b) and the “Gas Market Report 2022” (IEA, 2022a).

Furthermore, the evolution of the MGO price is estimated by applying the oil price evolution foreseen in the “Stated Policy Scenario” of the World Energy Outlook 2022 (IEA, 2022b) to the real market price of 2021. With these data it is possible to estimate the variable cost of the marginal CCGT according to the following equation:

$$VC_{CCGT} = \frac{C_{Ngas}}{\eta} + \frac{C_{CO2} \cdot EF_{CO2}}{\eta} + VOM \quad (6)$$

Where η is the efficiency of the CCGT set equal to 56%, EF_{CO2} is the carbon emission factor of natural gas equal to 0.0555 t/GJ and VOM is the Variable Operating and Maintenance cost set equal to 5 €2021/MWh.

Figure 4 reports the cost evolutions according to the formulated assumptions. Thus, the final fee for the cold ironing will be given by the connection fee plus the electricity cost which is set

equal to the CCGT cost reported in Figure 4. The final fee is to be compared with the on-board generation cost given by the MGO fuel consumption multiplied for its cost, whose evolution is shown in Figure 4.

The final result is that if cold ironing is considered, a total of 9 M€ is saved in terms of energy cost within a period of 30 years. This is a very conservative estimation since it does not take into account the possibility that renewables could change the system price on the power market. For example, the LCOE of a PV plant, that could be the technology substituting the CCGT in peak hours, is much lower than the CCGT variable cost (i.e., about 30€/MWh vs. 90€/MWh).

Figure 4. Air pollutant emissions and carbon emissions in case of on-board and onshore energy supply during the hotelling phase for a cruise ship.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The present work proposes the development of a pre-feasibility analysis of a cold ironing system for supporting the in-port operation of a cruise ship. Energy, environmental, and economic considerations are illustrated, and some conclusions can be derived, as reported in the following.

- The utilization of a cold ironing system determines a reduction of fossil fuel consumption by considering the current composition of the Italian power generation mix. Looking at the future evolution of the generation mix, the context should become even more convenient since more renewables are expected to enter in operation.

- The cold ironing system guarantees a substantial decrease of air pollutant emissions and greenhouse gases. This is relevant since in most cases cruise terminals are located in city centres thus emissions have a direct impact on the urban population. Cold ironing system can contribute to reduce the emissions locally, but also globally since the current configuration of the Italian power system determines an overall lower level of emissions with respect to on-board generation.
- The economic analysis of the cold ironing demonstrated its viability especially from the point of view of reduction in externalities. The substantial reduction in pollutant emissions has a strong effect in reducing the externality costs, thus cold ironing results more convenient for the community. In terms of operating cost, cold ironing determines an overall saving

of 9 M€, but most of it is achieved in the long term.

The proposed estimations are affected by the different considered assumptions and by the uncertainty of many data. A further development of this study could be represented by the implementation of a scenario analysis to evaluate the impact of different fuel evolutions.

Furthermore, the switching from a deterministic to a probabilistic approach in the calculation would allow to estimate the risk connected with this investment in order to take more informed decisions.

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